

The Harmonic System

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Abstract

Questions and Answers with proofs that relate to my two previous papers The Harmonic System [1] dated 15th May 2022 and The Harmonic System [2] dated 26th May 2022.

The relationships between prime numbers, harmonics, the pattern in prime numbers, the harmonic system, the natural number system, and the Riemann hypothesis.

The (natural) Number System

- 1 Does the (natural) number system have base 10 counting system?
 - a. Answer: no.
 - b. Reason and Proof: Choose a prime number for example 2. Count from that for example 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ... This demonstrates that prime number 2 is a counting system. Call it counting system 2. Where $2 < 10$. Where $12 > 10$. Where $2 \neq 10$. Therefore $10 \neq$ prime. Therefore the (natural) number system has base 2 counting system and not base 10 counting system. However counting system 2 does not make up the whole (natural) number system. To demonstrate where the rest of the (natural) number system comes from choose another prime number for example 3. Count from that for example 3, 6, 9, 12 ... This demonstrates that prime number 3 is a counting system. Call it counting system 3. Therefore in the same way each prime number is the base for its own counting system where all different counting systems coexist at the same time. Therefore the natural number system has quantum state base numbers. Each quantum state base is a prime number that becomes a quantum state counting system with its harmonics. Therefore the (natural) number system formula is $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ that represents the whole (natural) number system made up of quantum bases and their harmonics. Where (n) means excluding the repeat of each shared harmonic. This is where a shared harmonic (for example 6, being the second harmonic of 2, and the first harmonic of 3) is present once and is not repeated (n). Therefore each number appears once and all numbers are a harmonic and where a base = a zero harmonic. Therefore all the different numbers have equal importance creating the whole (natural) number system.
 - c. Proof formula: $10 \neq$ prime.
- 2 Is number 1 the first number in the (natural) number system?
 - a. Answer: no.
 - b. Reason and Proof: As can be seen by the (natural) number system formula $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ This shows that 1 is the whole made up of all counting systems where (n) means a shared harmonic is not repeated thereby creating the (natural) number system where each number appears once. This includes where each fraction represents a proportion of the whole and where proportions create harmony. Also all numbers 2 onwards represent frequencies where each have a present state (made up of a

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number for example 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ... for counting system 2) and a non-present state (made up of a gap for example 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 ... for counting system 2). Or it can be interpreted that each frequency has what appears to match an oscillation with one side matching the present state (made up of a number for example 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ... for counting system 2) and the opposite side that matches the non-present state (for example 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 ... for counting system 2). Therefore 1 is a constant that does not have a present and non-present state. Therefore 1 does not represent an oscillation. Or 1 is a state that does not represent an oscillation of itself. Therefore 1 does not have an alternating state. Therefore 1 is always on or in the present state. Therefore in the context that all numbers represent frequencies then $1 \neq$ number. Therefore $1 = 1/2$ is the first counting system made up of all even numbers. Therefore $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ Therefore 2 is the first number. Therefore frequency $2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ is the only frequency that has its alternating states as whole numbers (for example on one side there is 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ... and on the alternating side to that there is 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 ...). This demonstrates that frequency 2 is the line of symmetry in the (natural) number system. All odd numbers have an alternating position with a non-whole number making them impossible to be the line of symmetry. For example $1/3 = 3, 6, 9, 12 \dots$ on one side and on the alternating side to those there is 4.5, 7.5, 10.5, 13.5 ...). It is put forward here as a theory that the (natural) number system as represented by $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ represents the structure of a harmonic field that is made up of harmonics and is the fundamental structure of all, and from which all forms originate or come from, both physically, non-physically and otherwise. This field could be described as The Harmonic System (in the context of Harmonic System 2 being a pattern in itself made up of the prime and its harmonics, where that structure as a whole is repeated as a fractal pattern to form each counting system, where each shared harmonic is not repeated (n) and in turn the whole field is created.) Therefore this field as a whole could be called The Harmonic System as $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ or The Harmonic System Field. In this way the name The Harmonic System for a counting system is a fractal of the whole (natural) number system representing the field also called The Harmonic System. Or another name for this whole field could be The Harmonic Field or The Frequency Field. Other well-known names for example could apply. Such other names could include The Akashic Field, Akasha [3] where "In Hinduism, akasha means the basis and essence of all things in the material world, the first element created." (Under subheading "Hinduism" line 1). The Field, The Unified Field, The Matrix, The Quantum Field, or other suitable name along these lines. This field is made unified by its harmonics.

c. Proof formula: $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$

3 Is there a pattern in prime numbers?

a. Answer: yes.

b. Reason and Proof: Choose a prime number for example 2. Count from that for example 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ... (counting system 2). Choose another prime number for example 3 and count from that 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 ... (counting system 3). And so on for as many prime number counting systems you choose. Where all counting systems make up the (natural) number system shown by the number system formula $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ where each shared harmonic is not repeated (n). Therefore there are two parts to a counting system: the prime number and its harmonics, and they are a function of each other. Therefore each prime and its harmonics are complementary to each other. This is the same for light and shadow. When there is a shadow there is light. They are a function of each other. So you don't ask the question

– what shadow does the shadow make? To look at the shadow without the light is to look at the prime without the harmonics. And you don't ask the question – what is the pattern in the harmonics? Therefore the question of the pattern in prime numbers is to be read as the pattern in prime numbers together with their harmonics. Therefore a counting system is the structure for this pattern. That is made up of the prime and its harmonics, known as a Harmonic System. Therefore Harmonic System 2 being prime 2 and its harmonics is the first Harmonic System. Therefore that pattern is repeated as a fractal creating the (natural) number system (where a shared harmonic is not repeated (n) so each number appears once) as shown by the pattern in prime numbers formula $[1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots 1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots 1/5n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 \dots] = [1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots]$.

c. Proof formula: $[1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots 1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots 1/5n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 \dots] = [1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots]$

4 Can the pattern in prime numbers be seen?

a. Answer: yes.

b. Reason and Proof: The number system formula $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ has quantum state base numbers. Each base is a prime number that has harmonics. For example $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ (counting system 2) and $1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots$ (counting system 3 integrated with other bases) and the same goes with all counting systems. Harmonic System 2 with its prime 2 and first four harmonics 4, 6, 8, 10 being the first 5 numbers of Harmonic System 2 are shown below on the next page.

Each circle represents a number. As each Harmonic System is repeated as a fractal pattern these are also the first 5 numbers of all Harmonic Systems. For each number above the 5th circle there would be another circle off the page representing a whole Harmonic System. Each number is in a quantum state of being both the prime and the harmonic. Therefore for frequency system 2 that is $2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$. Therefore $2 = 4$ (or $2 + 2$). $2 = 6$ (or $2 + 2 + 2$). $2 = 8$ (or $2 + 2 + 2 + 2$). And so on. At the same time 2 is the common denominator of all its harmonics as the base. Therefore the same principles apply to all Harmonic Systems. At any scale the design of each Harmonic System is the same. Therefore $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ where $1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots$ (counting system 3 as integrated with other bases) and the same goes with all counting systems also known as frequency systems or Harmonic Systems. Therefore The Harmonic System has the design of a counting system that is shown above as a pattern that is repeated as a fractal pattern to create the (natural) number system as shown by the pattern in prime numbers formula $[1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots \quad 1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots \quad 1/5n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 \dots] = [1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots]$

- c. Proof formula: $[1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots \quad 1/3n = 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 \dots \quad 1/5n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 \dots] = [1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots]$

5 Is a prime number a building block?

- a. Answer: no.
 b. Reason and Proof: As $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ is the first Harmonic System, that is all even numbers on frequency 2. Therefore that is frequency system 2. That includes all first harmonic or 1h, where all 1h exist before a prime number does. As 2 is a fractal of $1/2$ that means the fundamental or base number is $2p / 2 = p$ (where $p = \text{prime}$). The prime number is created from the first harmonic. Therefore $1h / 2$. Therefore if there is to be a building block description that is the first harmonic or 1h. Therefore 1h is a standard unit from which all primes are formed. Therefore a prime number is not a building block but is a harmonic defined as a zero harmonic or 0h. Therefore $1h / 2 = 0h$. Therefore $0h = \text{fundamental frequency}$. Therefore all primes are in frequency 2 at 1h. Therefore all 1h are in primes.
 c. Proof formula: $1h / 2 = 0h$

6 Can a zero harmonic = a number?

- a. Answer: yes.
 b. Reason and Proof: When the baseline standard unit of a frequency is 1h the standard language or universal language is in harmonics and not in prime numbers. Not in fundamental frequencies, that is prime numbers. This is because harmony exists before a number does. This is because the first Harmonic System is 2 and has the baseline of 1h. The fractal of $1/2$ is 2 which means the reduced numbers on frequency 2 are all numbers that can be divided by 2 to produce a fundamental frequency. For example $1h (22) / 2 = 0h (11)$. Therefore $1h / 2 = 0h$. This creates the fundamental frequency of each prime number that has no repeat of itself in that state as 0h. Therefore a zero harmonic or $0h = \text{a number, a prime number, a fundamental frequency}$. It is put forward here as a theory that the Harmonic System Field (as referred to earlier) that can also be called The Harmonic System (as referred to earlier) was formed as follows 1) the formation of frequency 2 in quantum state 2) the formation of all fundamental frequencies (from all first harmonics) in quantum state 3) the formation of all harmonics in quantum state, based on each fundamental frequency (1h is already formed so that is simply re-stated from a different point of view of the fundamental frequency, and all 2nd

harmonics onwards). Therefore this Harmonic System Field formula is $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$

c. Proof formula: $1h / 2 = 0h$

The Riemann hypothesis

- 1 Is the Riemann hypothesis real part $1/2$ of the complex number connected to the pattern in prime numbers?
 - a. Answer: yes.
 - b. Reason and Proof: To re-cap the Riemann hypothesis is referred to by Enrico Bombieri [4] where all nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function have real part = $1/2$. As shown the pattern in prime numbers is two things being one the pattern of a Harmonic System that is the prime and its harmonics. Two the Harmonic System pattern such as Harmonic System 2 pattern being repeated by each different Harmonic System forming a fractal pattern that represents the whole Harmonic Field (as referred to earlier, also called The Harmonic System Field). Therefore that is represented by the (natural) number system seen by the formula $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ where there is no repeat of a shared harmonic (n). The connection is that the real part $1/2$ of the Riemann is actually the real $1/2$ of the (natural) number system as in $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ which is frequency system 2. This is the line of symmetry of the number system making up 1 in 2 of all numbers being all even numbers on the single frequency of 2. The alternating states of these are all whole odd numbers 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 ... The other numbers to frequency 2 making up 1 in 2 of all numbers (that is all odd numbers) are not all on the same fundamental frequency (for example 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 15, 17 ...) As the fractal of $1/2$ is 2 frequency 2 numbers are reduced to the 1h of all fundamental frequency numbers (that is $2 = 6, 10, 14, 22, 26 \dots$). Therefore [the real part $1/2$] = [$1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ that is the pattern and Harmonic Field $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ Where $1h / 2 = 0h$]
 - c. Proof formula: [the real part $1/2$] = [$1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ that is the pattern and Harmonic Field $1 = 1/2 + 1/3n + 1/4n + 1/5n \dots$ Where $1h / 2 = 0h$]

- 2 Does the distribution of prime numbers (in relation to each other) reveal the meaning of them?
 - a. Answer: no.
 - b. Reason and Proof: The need to know the distribution of prime numbers arose when the position of the prime numbers could not be predicted. The need to predict prime numbers arose to find their meaning. Each prime number is the fundamental frequency that with its harmonics create a Harmonic System. The distribution of prime numbers in their own right do not take into account the harmonics of each prime. If a prime is a shadow a (1^{st}) harmonic is the light. Looking at the distribution of primes is like looking at multiple shadows apparently interrelating without looking at the multiple actual interrelating (1^{st}) harmonic lights. A prime is a function of its (1^{st}) harmonics. Each prime in a Harmonic System is distributed in relation to its first harmonic 1h. Therefore $1h / 2 = 0h$. Therefore the distribution of primes in relation to each other do not reveal their meaning however the distribution of primes in relation to the first harmonic 1h do reveal their meaning as a fundamental frequency 0h.
 - c. Proof formula: $1h / 2 = 0h$

- 3 Does the Riemann hypothesis equate to $1h / 2 = 0h$?
 - a. Answer: yes.

- b. Reason and Proof: The Riemann Zeta values are a function of each other. The real part $1/2$ of the complex number is $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ of the number system where $1h / 2 = 0h$. The Zeta 0 corresponds to $0h$ being a prime whilst at the same time being on the $1/2$ line of $1/2 = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \dots$ as the line of symmetry. Therefore the imaginary (i) Riemann value on frequency $2 = x^2$ of its base value or is $i1h$. Therefore the Riemann imaginary number (i) is $i1h$ with the real part $1/2 = 0$ means $[i + 1/2 = 0] = [i1h + 1/2 = i0h]$. Therefore $[i + 1/2 = 0] = [i1h + 1/2 = i0h] = [i1h / 2 = i0h] = [1h / 2 = 0h]$. Therefore the Riemann hypothesis is supported because all non-trivial zeros of the Zeta function can only be on the $1/2$ line, or frequency 2. It can be described that the $i1h$ values do not land there from being graphed but are hard wired on frequency 2. They are frequency 2. This means (i) = the imaginary base that is the value of an imaginary harmonic system. This imaginary aspect is there because the values deal with distribution of primes and not their actual position. If there was no distribution of primes the values would be of a real prime with real harmonics representing a real harmonic system.
- c. Proof formula: $[i + 1/2 = 0] = [i1h + 1/2 = i0h] = [i1h / 2 = i0h] = [1h / 2 = 0h]$

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